

SMAUG 2nd Newsletter!

Explore the latest news and activities of the SMAUG project!

Dear Readers,

The SMAUG project is continuing its journey in the seas of research and development! Just a few months before the conclusion of its first year, currently, in month 8 of its implementation, the project has made progress towards its objectives while delivering some preliminary results. In this issue, we will explore the project's latest activities, such as event participation, technical articles, meetings, and interesting reads.

Let's sail away with the SMAUG project!

PORT OF CALL LATEST NEWS & EVENTS

Port of call: Latest News & Events

Even though it is still in its early stages, the SMAUG project participated in significant events, spreading the word about its aims and objectives.

SMAUG project in CERIS event in Brussels!

SMAUG in CERIS Event!

The SMAUG project gladly accepted the invitation to participate in the **CERIS workshop on Innovation for Maritime Situational Awareness and Security**, held on Monday, 19 February 2024, in Brussels. SMAUG's involvement in CERIS extended beyond this day, continuing with a presentation on Wednesday, 21 February, at the "**CERIS workshop on Illicit Drugs: Challenges and Opportunities for Introducing Innovative and Science-Based Approaches**". The SMAUG project garnered significant interest during the CERIS event. It provided an excellent opportunity for the project to be explored in greater depth, disseminated widely, and engaged with interested stakeholders. Our reflections on the CERIS event highlight the valuable connections made with fellow participants, speakers, and industry experts. The networking sessions facilitated the exchange of ideas, discussion of challenges, and the formation of collaborations. These relationships are not merely professional connections but potential catalysts for future projects and collaborations that will enrich the research field.

[Read the full story](#)

Explore the CERIS event from the EU Commission's News Articles!

CERIS Workshop on illicit drugs draws more than 100 participants to Brussels

[Learn more](#)

Innovation for Maritime Situational Awareness and Security

[Learn more](#)

SMAUG GA Meeting

On Wednesday 20th, and Thursday 21st of March, the SMAUG consortium members had the opportunity to attend the two-day General Assembly (GA) meeting in Madrid organized by the project's partner Universidad Politécnica de Madrid. GA meetings play a critical role in the project's success, while are a wonderful opportunity to coordinate efforts, share information, decisions making, and shaping the project's future roadmap.

[Read the full story of the SMAUG GA meeting here](#)

**And now, the time has come for a short trip into
Maritime Transportation History!**

From the earliest days of human civilisation, the vast and enigmatic expanse of the world's oceans has invited explorers, traders, and adventurers. Since ancient times, there is evidence that sea transportation has been extensively utilised. The foundation of international trade and the world's economy has its roots in maritime transportation! This article embarks on a brief journey through time, presenting the current challenges as well!

[Read the full article](#)

SMAUG #Tech Unveiled

The SMAUG project is on a mission to improve the underwater detection of threats in ports and their entrance routes using an integrated system capable of providing data concerning threat analysis between three main elements: **Ports security infrastructure, Advanced underwater detection systems and Surveillance vessels**. Today, we will focus on Surveillance vessels and, more precisely, on **USV (Uncrewed Surface Vessel)**! Lemvos, SMAUG's consortium partner and leader of Work Package 5 (Smart Integration of Data sources), is bringing to the project a cutting-edge USV (Uncrewed Surface Vessel), which will also be utilised and adapted accordingly to fit the SMAUG project pilots.

Sounds exciting? Click to learn more about SMAUG USV technology

SMAUG partners interviews!

Join us on the collective journey we are embarking upon to a safer maritime environment!

The SMAUG consortium comprises **22 highly experienced partners** across **7 EU countries (Spain, Italy, France, Germany, Greece, Norway, Estonia)** under **Indra's coordination**.

In this issue we are presenting a short interview with our project coordinator!

We start this journey with the project's coordinator, Juan-Román Martínez Arranz from Indra!

SMAUG Deliverables

During the first eight months of the SMAUG's project implementation, we submitted three deliverables successfully under collaborative efforts. Deliverables **D1.2 Consultation Strategy**, **D1.3 Data Management Plan**, and **D7.1 Impact Master Plan** have been submitted, including information about the project's consultation strategy to get feedback from stakeholders and establish a longer-term relationship of mutual benefit and trust, all the detailed insights on how the project will handle and the process store of its data produced and collected and the project's strategies for dissemination, exploitation, and communication accordingly.

[Explore the SMAUG Deliverables](#)

Interesting read!

What are maritime crime and maritime security?

SMAUG project aims to build a safer port and maritime environment using a state-of-the-art integrated system. But in order to speak about securing ports

and their entrance routes, we need to define maritime challenges, crimes and potential security threats. *“The term Maritime Security means different things to different people, while Maritime Crime, whereas perhaps easier to define, has been neglected by criminologists and crime scientists whose perspective has largely remained landlocked.”* A highly interesting quote from the **What are Maritime Crime and maritime security?** article which was published from the International Journal of Maritime Crime & Security (IJMCS).

Explore the full story

What's next?

The SMAUG project will continue to work towards the achievement of its goals whereas soon it will celebrate its 12 months of implementation! In the meantime, it will publish blog articles, participate in events, conferences, and workshops, and collaborate with relevant EU projects, maximising its impact and reach and assisting in future research.

Join the SMAUG project's journey by following its social media profiles!

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SMAUG EU project

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